

Origin of the magnetism in undoped and Mn-doped SnO₂ thin films: Sn versus oxygen vacancies

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ABSTRACT: SnO₂ and Mn-doped SnO₂ thin films have been grown by rf sputtering in two different atmospheres (Ar and Ar/O₂) on Si(100) and Al₂O₃ (R-cut) at room temperature (RT) and at 500°C. The RT grown films are amorphous while those grown at 500°C are polycrystalline or epitaxial depending on the substrate. All the films, undoped or Mn-doped, present a paramagnetic signal and ferromagnetism is not observed, regardless of the growth conditions or of their structure. The measured magnetization systematically decreases when the films are grown in oxygen free atmosphere, thus indicating that magnetism is not promoted by oxygen vacancies and no correlation is found between conductivity and magnetism. We compare the experimental results with *ab-initio* density functional calculations and demonstrate that the Sn vacancies are the origin of the measured magnetization in SnO₂ undoped films. Oxygen vacancies neither contribute to the magnetic moment nor to the conductivity of the samples. The localized nature of the defect induced electronic levels prevents a collective magnetic or conducting behaviour.

KEYWORDS: magnetic oxides, thin films, *ab-initio* calculations, wide band gap oxides, X-ray absorption spectroscopy,

1. INTRODUCTION

SnO_2 is a multifunctional oxide which combines several interesting properties as transparency and conductivity, and likely ferromagnetism in low dimensional structures.^{1,2} Therefore, thin films and heterostructures based on tin oxides are important both in the field of flexible electronics and as magnetic semiconductors. Room temperature ferromagnetism (FM) has been observed in transition metal doped and undoped tin oxide thin layers, nanosized compounds and heterostructures^{3,4,5,6,7} with a large variation of the estimated magnetic moment per doping ion. But paramagnetism (PM) has also been reported in analogous samples.^{7,8} Besides the discrepancy among the experimental results, the origin of the observed FM is still uncertain⁹ and its relation to the concentration of free carriers has certainly not been elucidated. The unintentional *n*-type conductivity of SnO_2 has been attributed to point defects, in particular to oxygen vacancies (O_{vac}), which have also been associated to the appearance of FM in SnO_2 thin films since the oxygen vacancies could give rise to magnetic centres and also to free carriers, which mediate the magnetic interaction.¹⁰ Nevertheless, according to recent calculations, oxygen vacancies cannot be the cause of the SnO_2 conductivity, since they produce deep impurity levels.¹¹ Therefore, the mechanism behind the high conductivity as well as the correlation between magnetism and oxygen vacancies are still controversial. Here, we show that oxygen vacancies are neither associated with the magnetic centres formed in undoped SnO_2 thin films nor with free carriers mediating long range ferromagnetic order among Mn ions. Most importantly, by combining the growth of undoped and Mn doped SnO_2 films under different conditions with density functional calculations, we prove that Sn vacancies (Sn_{vac}) are the origin of the observed paramagnetic signal. Moreover, the localization of the uncompensated holes and electrons raised by the point defects, as i.e. Sn and O vacancies, prevents the development of long range magnetic order, demonstrating that ferromagnetic correlations are not established neither in undoped SnO_2 nor in Mn: SnO_2 films in the dilute random regime.

2. EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATION DETAILS

SnO₂ thin films, undoped and doped with 4% of Mn, have been grown by sputtering on Si(100) and Al₂O₃ (R-cut) substrates. Different growth conditions as substrate temperature, T_s=25 or 500°C, and sputtering gas, Ar/O₂ (in the relation 2/1) or pure Ar, were used to grow the films. The thickness of all the films is around 200 nm and was deduced from X-ray reflectometry. The chemical composition of one of the Mn doped film was obtained by Rutherford back scattering (RBS) yielding a composition of 4% Mn over 96% of Sn. The undoped and Mn-doped SnO₂ thin films structures have been characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) in the standard configuration, θ -2 θ , with $\lambda=1.5406$ Å. We also used a configuration especially adequate for non epitaxial or textured thin films (i.e. for amorphous and polycrystalline films) which is the grazing incidence mode (GIXRD) at the BM25 Beamline at the ESRF (European Synchrotron Radiation Facility) using an incident energy of 14 keV ($\lambda=0.8857$ Å). The use of synchrotron radiation combined with a low incidence angle (in the present case 0.75°), is the optimum configuration to detect possible spurious/secondary phases. For the electronic characterization of the Mn-doped SnO₂ samples, Mn K-edge X-ray absorption measurements (XAS) were performed at the BM25 Beamline (ESRF). XAS in the near edge region is an element sensitive technique useful to obtain information on the oxidation state of the corresponding element in samples grown with different deposition parameters.¹² In the present study we have investigated the oxidation state of Mn depending on the growth conditions, i.e: growth atmosphere and substrate temperature. Since Sn presents two stable oxides, SnO₂ and SnO, with 4+ and 2+ oxidation states, respectively, ¹¹⁹Sn Mössbauer spectroscopy in the emission mode were performed to obtain the oxidation states of Sn.¹³ This technique indicates that Sn is in the 4+ state for either amorphous or crystalline undoped films. Nevertheless, a previous study on Mn/SnO₂ multilayers⁷ showed the existence of 30% of Sn²⁺ related to the presence of Mn in contact to SnO₂. Therefore, we cannot rule out the presence of a small fraction of Sn²⁺ and the Mossbauer technique gives an upper limit of 1-2% to Sn in the 2+ valence state.

The magnetic properties have been measured up to 5 T with a *Quantum Design* Superconducting Quantum Interference Device (SQUID). Special care has been taken during growth and handling of the samples to avoid any magnetic contamination. The samples were measured by fitting them into a straw without any capsule or cotton to avoid uncontrolled magnetic contributions.¹⁴ The diamagnetic signal corresponding to the substrate has been subtracted in all the curves. Transport measurements have been obtained in a four contacts configuration with a Keithley 2400 sourcemeter while for highly resistive samples two contacts configuration and voltage source were used.

A *first-principles* approach has been employed to calculate the electronic structure of SnO₂ and Mn:SnO₂ crystals with and without different point defects, either isolated or associated in complex. Our calculations are based on density functional theory within the local spin density (LSDA) approximation for the exchange and correlation functional. For the Mn:SnO₂ structures LSDA+U calculations, with the empirical Coulomb $U=4$ eV and exchange $J=0.8$ eV parameters chosen to model the orbital dependent Hubbard-like potential for the Mn d states, have been performed.¹⁵ The LSDA+U approach introduces correlation and localization effects beyond the LSDA and provides an improved description of impurity Mn states. We use the SIESTA package with basis sets formed by multiple-zeta polarized localized numerical atomic orbitals (AO).¹⁶ For Sn and O we choose double-zeta (DZ) basis for the s and p AOs plus a single-zeta (SZ) d AO, whereas for Mn we employ DZ for s and d and SZ for p AOs. Point defects and impurities are simulated using 48 atoms supercells with periodic boundary conditions, which correspond to defect concentrations of about 6%. A 8x8x12 mesh of Monkhorst-Pack points for integration over the Brillouin zone was used. The lattice parameters and all the atomic positions were allowed to relax until the forces on the atoms are less than 0.03 eV/Å.

SnO₂ crystallizes in the rutile structure with the P4/mnm space group, each Sn is sixfold coordinated with oxygen, while each O atom is threefold coordinated with Sn. The calculated equilibrium lattice parameters, $a= 4.74$ Å and $c= 3.19$ Å, are within 0.1% of the experimental values.

The fundamental band gap is direct at Γ and takes a value of 1.8 eV, in agreement with previous calculations^{17,18}, but small compared to the reported optical gap of 3.60 eV.¹⁹

As it is known LSDA underestimates the excited states energy and then yields too small band gap values of metal oxides, despite the ground state properties are well described²⁰. In fact, the calculated direct character of the SnO₂ gap, as well as the large dispersion of the lowest conduction band at Γ are consistent with optical measurements and with the characteristic band structure features of a good transparent conducting oxide.^{21,22} In the calculation of the Mn-doped SnO₂, the main effect of the LSDA+U approach was to increase the splitting between t_{2g} and e_g Mn derived impurity states although the orbital occupancy as well as the metallic or insulator character of the systems are similar in both LSDA and LSDA+U approaches.

3. RESULTS

The different growth conditions and substrates allow obtaining SnO₂ films with different textures, ranging from amorphous to epitaxial. Fig. 1 shows XRD data for representative SnO₂ films of different textures. When grown at room temperature, amorphous films for both, undoped and Mn-doped, are always obtained (Fig. 1(a)), while at 500°C they grow polycrystalline on Si (Fig. 1(c)) and epitaxial, textured along the [101] direction, on sapphire R-cut substrates (Fig. 1(b)). A small fraction of (200) oriented grains is observed for the Mn:SnO₂ film grown on sapphire in an Ar/O₂ atmosphere. The substrate peaks (corresponding to Si or to sapphire), labelled with S, are detected in the standard configuration but not in GIXRD, as expected. Logarithmic scales are used to enhance possible very low intensity peaks related to spurious/secondary phases. These data exclude the formation of spurious phases within the detection limits of the synchrotron diffraction techniques. The lattice parameters ($a=b=4.743$ Å, $c=3.186$ Å) obtained for the polycrystalline undoped SnO₂ film grown on Si(100) in an Ar atmosphere are almost identical to the SnO₂ bulk values ($a=b=4.738$ Å, $c=3.187$ Å). The bulk like lattice parameters discard a significant content of defects inside the grains, which, whether exists, will be mostly confined to the grain boundaries. However, epitaxial

undoped films deposited on sapphire present a larger (101) interplanar distance $d_{(101)}=2.659 \text{ \AA}$ than the bulk value (2.644 \AA). The increase of the out of plane parameter is usually associated, in epitaxial films, to a decrease of the in-plane parameters induced by the substrate.³

Figure 1. (Color online) XRD of Mn-doped (red and blue) and undoped (black) SnO₂ films grown on different substrates, temperature and deposition atmosphere: (a) amorphous: $T_s=25^\circ\text{C}$ on Si, (b) epitaxial: $T_s=500^\circ\text{C}$ on Al₂O₃ (c) (101) diffraction peaks for the epitaxial films (linear intensity scale) (d) polycrystalline: $T_s=500^\circ\text{C}$ on Si. “S”= substrate peaks.

The variation of the (101) interplanar distance of the Mn-doped films has opposite sign depending on the growth atmosphere, Ar or Ar/O₂. The shift occurs to lower angles for samples grown in an Ar atmosphere and to higher angles for those grown in Ar/O₂. The inset of Fig. 1 evidences the shifts of the (101) diffraction peak of epitaxial 4% Mn-doped films compared to the undoped film. The behaviour is analogous for the epitaxial and polycrystalline films. Since the ionic radius of Sn⁴⁺ is 0.74 Å and the radii of Mn ions are 0.90 Å for Mn²⁺, 0.70 Å for Mn³⁺ and 0.50 Å for Mn⁴⁺, the incorporation of some Mn²⁺ to the SnO₂ lattice can explain the observed lattice expansion for films grown in Ar. The contraction measured for the Mn:SnO₂ films grown in Ar/O₂ point to a higher oxidation state, Mn³⁺. Further, the observed changes of the SnO₂ lattice parameters strongly support the incorporation of Mn into the SnO₂ lattice.

Figure 2. (Color online) (a) XANES spectra at the Mn K-edge of the Mn oxides references (MnO: Mn²⁺, Mn₂O₃: Mn³⁺ and MnO₂: Mn⁴⁺) and of Mn:SnO₂ films grown on Si(001) in the different conditions: open symbols for the films grown in Ar/O₂ atmosphere and filled symbols for those grown in Ar. Circles correspond to films grown at 25°C and triangles for those grown at 500°C. (b) Derivatives of the sample spectra and of the Mn²⁺ and Mn³⁺ references.

The incorporation of Mn to the SnO₂ lattice with different valence states depending on the growth atmosphere suggested by the XRD results agrees with Mn K-edge XAS measurements in Mn-doped SnO₂ samples (Fig. 2(a)): the comparison of these spectra with Mn reference oxides (MnO: Mn²⁺, Mn₂O₃: Mn³⁺ and MnO₂: Mn⁴⁺) reveals that, in Ar grown films, Mn is a combination of 2+ and 3+ formal oxidation states with a predominance of Mn²⁺. On the other hand, the samples grown in Ar/O₂ clearly present a more oxidized state of Mn that coincides very well with the Mn XAS signal of Mn₂O₃ and also agrees with the lattice contraction due to the smaller ionic radius of Mn³⁺. The derivatives of the thin film spectra compared with those corresponding to Mn²⁺ and Mn³⁺ references are depicted in Fig. 2(b) evidencing their similarities. The inflection point of the energy edge, which corresponds to a maximum in the derivatives, is often used to extract the oxidation state from the linear relationship between its energy and its formal oxidation state in series of chemically similar Mn-compounds (based on Kunzl law²³). Although it is not straightforward to define these energies since shapes of the thin film derivatives are complex, we have estimated that samples grown in Ar contain Mn in a valence state intermediate between 2+ and 3+, of approximately 2.4+. The derivatives of films deposited with Ar/O₂, are similar to Mn³⁺ derivative spectrum and an estimated formal valence of 3.2+ is obtained.

Figure 3. (Color online) Magnetization (in emu/cm^3) at 5 K of SnO_2 films grown in Ar (circles) and Ar/O_2 (squares) atmospheres of (a) amorphous undoped SnO_2 on Si (b) amorphous Mn-doped on Si (c) polycrystalline Mn-doped on Si and (d) epitaxial Mn-doped on sapphire. The lines are fits to the Brillouin function. (e) Magnetization at 5 K of amorphous SnO_2 and Mn: SnO_2 films compared with the Si(100) substrate signal in emu normalized to the sample weight.

Magnetic loops at 5 K of undoped and 4% Mn-doped amorphous films grown on Si, in both Ar/O_2 and Ar atmospheres are presented in Fig. 3(a)-(b). Similar results are obtained for the films grown in sapphire at 25°C . Panels (c)-(d) represent those corresponding to Mn: SnO_2 samples grown at 500°C both polycrystalline (c) and epitaxial (d). In Fig. 3(e) we present the comparison of the magnetic signals of a highly resistive Si(100) substrate and of an amorphous SnO_2 and a Mn: SnO_2 film grown on Si normalized to the sample (mainly substrate) weight after removal of the diamagnetic contribution: the SnO_2 signal is clearly distinguishable from the substrate one. The

fitted thin film magnetizations using Brillouin functions, as described in Ref. 7, are also shown in Fig. 3(a)-(d). All the films show paramagnetic behaviour, independently of their microstructure and growth conditions. Even the undoped SnO₂ samples present a net magnetization, although the signals are more than one order of magnitude smaller than those of the Mn:SnO₂ films. The highest number of magnetic centres is reached for the amorphous Mn-doped sample grown in an O₂ rich environment. We have estimated the number of magnetic centres from the Brillouin fits of the magnetization cycles and they result to be in the range of 10⁻³/unit cell for undoped SnO₂. Further, for the Mn-doped films, the estimated number of Mn's contributing to the paramagnetic signal is significantly lower than that expected for a 4% Mn concentration. This low magnetization is most probably due to the existence of close Mn pairs antiferromagnetically coupled, as it occurs in Mn/SnO₂ multilayers with higher Mn concentration.⁷

The magnetic moments per centre (MM) obtained from the angular moments (J) estimated from the Brillouin fits are 6 μ_B/per centre for the undoped samples, 3.8 μ_B/per Mn (J=1.9) for Mn-doped films grown in Ar/O₂ and 5.2 μ_B/per Mn (J=2.6) for those in Ar. The magnetic moments per Mn ion correspond well to those expected for Mn³⁺ (3d⁴, J=2) and Mn²⁺ (3d⁵, J=5/2) states, respectively, and coincide with the XAS results (Fig. 2).

In all the samples analysed, the growth in an Ar atmosphere, which facilitates the formation of O_{vac}, reduces the magnetization of both pure and Mn-doped SnO₂ films. Therefore, our results indicates that oxygen vacancies do not contribute to the magnetization, in fact they seem to favour the reduction of the number of magnetic centres even for Mn:SnO₂ films where despite the increase of the MM per centre for the samples grown in an Ar atmosphere, the total magnetization decreases indicating a reduction of the number of magnetic centres. Because tin forms two stable oxides with Sn⁴⁺ and Sn²⁺ valence states, it is likely that O_{vac} can be partially locally compensated by a coordination of Sn analogous to that of SnO.²⁴

Figure 4. (Color online) Conductivity (σ) vs. saturation magnetization (M_s) for SnO_2 (circles) and $\text{Mn}:\text{SnO}_2$ (squares) films grown in different conditions. The lines connect pairs of films whose sole difference is the oxygen atmosphere.

Fig. 4 represents the conductivity of the SnO_2 films grown on highly insulating Al_2O_3 substrates versus the magnetization. Note that Si substrates are not adequate for transport measurements of resistive films. Fig. 4 evidences that there is no correlation between magnetization and conductivity. Even more, the behaviour of the conductivity with the gas atmosphere during the growth, is opposite for Mn-doped and undoped samples. Mn-doped films grown in an oxygen rich atmosphere, which show the largest magnetization, exhibit the lower conductivity. Conversely, for pure SnO_2 films the conductivity increases with the magnetization and thus with the oxygen pressure. Nevertheless, we would like to stress that transport in thin films is a complicated process and always strongly influenced by the morphology, inter-grain interfaces or grain sizes.

Figure 5. (Color online) Spin-resolved DOS of (a) a pure SnO_2 crystals and SnO_2 with point defects: (b) Sn_{vac} , (c) O_{vac} , and (d) a complex defect formed by adjacent $\text{Sn}_{\text{vac}} + \text{O}_{\text{vac}}$. Positive (negative) values represent majority (minority) spin states. Blue lines correspond to total DOS, red lines to partial oxygen DOS and blue filled to Sn partial DOS. The Fermi level of the pure SnO_2 crystal is the zero of energy for all the figures (indicated by thin straight lines).

Spontaneous magnetization persistent above room temperature has been found in thin films and nanoparticles of several oxides in the absence of magnetic elements.^{25,26} The appearance of local magnetic moments has been attributed to the presence of localized holes in the valence band of the oxide, due to defects or surfaces.^{27,28,29} Thus, the paramagnetism observed in undoped SnO_2 might be attributed to the presence of native point defects.¹¹ To elucidate the origin of the magnetic centres, we have calculated the electronic properties of several point defects, from vacancies to interstitials, as well as complex defects. Fig. 5 shows the density of states (DOS) corresponding to several representative defects: oxygen (O_{vac}) and Sn (Sn_{vac}) vacancies and a complex defect formed by associating an O_{vac} and a Sn_{vac} . In the perfect crystal the Oxygen $2p$ states dominate the valence band maximum (VBM) while the Sn $5s$ states are the major component around the conduction band

minimum (CBM) (Fig. 5(a)). An O_{vac} induces states in the energy gap, mainly localized at the Sn atoms surrounding the vacancy (Fig. 5(c)). Nevertheless, the system remains insulator due to the ability of the SnO_2 to locally compensate the O_{vac} , as previously mentioned. However, a Sn_{vac} as well as a Sn interstitial (Sn_{int}), not shown in the Figure, give rise to a metallic state. The Fermi level crosses the VB for the Sn_{vac} and the CB for the Sn_{int} . The metallic character has its origin in the presence of uncompensated holes and electrons for the Sn_{vac} and Sn_{int} , respectively. Nevertheless, we found that only the Sn_{vac} induces a half-metal ground state, spontaneous spin polarization and then a large magnetic moment, $\text{MM}=3.63 \mu_{\text{B}}$, as evidences the density of states (DOS) of SnO_2 with 6% of Sn_{vac} shown in Fig. 5(b). The charge imbalance yields holes in the valence band of the oxide, and induces a spontaneous spin polarization; each neighbouring O atom to the Sn_{vac} acquires a MM of $0.5 \mu_{\text{B}}$. Further, adding an extra O_{vac} well separated from the Sn_{vac} does not alter neither the metallic character nor the magnetic moment of the defected crystal, only when the O_{vac} is nearest neighbour to the Sn_{vac} , the total MM reduces to $1.90 \mu_{\text{B}}$, as can be inferred from Fig. 5(d). The decrease is not only due to the loss of a polarized O but also to the diminished charge of the O surrounding the cation vacancy. The calculated reduced MM may partly account for the decrease of the magnetization observed in the films grown in O_2 poor atmosphere (Fig. 3(a)) although the decrease must be mainly originated by the reduction of the Sn_{vac} concentration due to the increase of its formation energy. Analogous calculations with supercells of different sizes, gives similar local electronic structure and MM, provided the size of the supercell is large enough to avoid direct interaction between defects.

Figure 6. (Color online) (a) Ground state after relaxation of the SnO₂ supercell with a Sn vacancy. Big red and small blue spheres represent O and Sn atoms, respectively. The Sn vacancy is symbolized by a white sphere and the [110] plane unit cell is indicated by the thin continuous line. (b) The spin density distribution in the [110] plane around the Sn vacancy. Contour lines correspond to step of 0.005 e/Bhor³ in a color scale between [0.0, 0.2].

The induced spin-polarization only extends up to O next nearest-neighbours close to the Sn_{vac}, as evidences Fig. 6., where the spin density of the oxygen atoms located at the [110] plane of the unit cell are represented. The magnetic moments are symmetrically distributed and all the oxygen close the Sn_{vac} develop equivalent spin polarization. Hence interaction between defect-induced magnetic moments would require percolation and a large concentration of defects, above 12%, which explains the observed paramagnetism and the absence of long range magnetic order in the undoped SnO₂ samples. Further, the localized nature of the induced holes also accounts for the low conductivity measured in the pure SnO₂ samples. Fig. 5 shows a slightly larger DOS in the case of an isolated Sn_{vac}, which may correspond with the slight increase of conductivity observed in the samples grown in a rich O₂ atmosphere. Nevertheless, as pointed out above, the dependence of the conductivity on the growth conditions seen in Fig. 4 evidences that the electrical behaviour is complex and may be mainly determined by the crystallinity and morphology of the film.

To simulate the Mn doping we substitute a Sn by a Mn (Mn_{sub}) in a 48 atom supercell (equivalent to a 6.25% doping). The octahedral coordination of the Mn ion splits the t_{2g} and e_g states. As seen in Fig. 7(a), only the t_{2g} states are occupied and hybridized with the nearest oxygen 2p states. As a

result Mn has a low MM (Table I) and a charge transfer of 1.09e (Mulliken charge³⁰). The Fermi level remains in the energy gap and thus the doped system is an insulator.

	Mn _{sub}	Mn _{int}	M _{sub} +O _{vac}	Mn _{int} + O _{vac}
MM _{Mn} (μ_B)	3.18	4.69	3.92	4.10
MM _{total} (μ_B)	3.00	4.92	3.84	3.31

Table I. Calculated magnetic moments (MM) for the Mn at either Mn_{sub} or Mn_{int} lattice positions with and without an O_{vac}. MM_{total} corresponds to the magnetic moment for the whole supercell. The induced MM in O is coupled antiparallel for Mn_{sub}, decreasing MM_{total}, while coupled parallel in the Mn_{int} case.

Since the XAS measurements show that in oxygen rich atmosphere Mn is on average in the Mn³⁺ state. We have also calculated the electronic properties of an interstitial Mn (Mn_{int}) in the SnO₂ lattice and the corresponding DOS and MM are also included in Fig. 7(b) and Table I respectively. Mn has a large MM due to the weaker interaction with the lattice, as confirmed by the low hybridization and charge transfer (0.87e) from Mn to the neighbouring atoms, In fact all the Mn spin up states are occupied and the system is metallic. This result indicates that in the dilute regime the Mn contributing to the paramagnetism of the sample would have a local coordination between those corresponding to the Mn_{sub} and Mn_{int} lattice positions, which agrees with the valence state and the 3.8 μ_B MM experimentally measured. Furthermore, it will introduce some distortion in the lattice, which explains that the largest magnetization was obtained for the amorphous films. Furthermore, the inclusion of an O_{vac} separated from the Mn atoms has a small influence and the MMs and charge transfer are almost unaltered. Only when the O_{vac} is nearest neighbour to Mn the MM are changed. However, the effect of the O_{vac} on the Mn MM depends on the lattice position and hence on the spin state. While the MM of Mn_{sub} increases in the presence of O_{vac}, it decreases for Mn_{int}, which corresponds to a lower and higher occupation of the Mn spin down states, respectively, as inferred from Table I. The reduced magnetization measured in the films grown in an O₂ poor atmosphere

must be the result of a delicate balance of the increase and decrease of the MM experienced by Mn in different lattice positions. In fact, in agreement with the calculated MM the decrease is larger for amorphous samples in which higher concentration of Mn_{int} in a high MM is expected. Nevertheless, the effect of the O_{vac} in the interaction among Mn's is almost null.

Figure 7. (Color online). Spin-resolved total DOS for SnO₂ doped with 6% of (a) Mn substitutional of Sn, Mn_{sub} , or (b) in an interstitial position, Mn_{int} . The spin majority and minority DOS are plotted in blue and red, respectively. The Fermi level is at zero energy and the filled regions correspond to the Mn contribution,

We have analysed the spin interaction by calculating SnO₂ supercells with two Mn in several close and separated configurations, both with and without O_{vac} . The results are similar for all of them, MMs and orbital occupancies are close to those corresponding to the one Mn cases. The exchange interaction, estimated as the energy difference between the ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic states, is in all cases small, of the order of a few meV, and thus paramagnetism (PM) is the ground state. Only when Mn's are nearest-neighbours the antiferromagnetic state is lower in energy. Finally, for all the investigated configurations, excepting the Mn_{sub} where the Fermi level lays in the gap see Fig. 7, E_F cuts the Sn CB states, although the overlap with the Mn derived states is very small. In particular, when an O_{vac} is located close to the Mn, i.e.: $Mn_{sub} + O_{vac}$ and $Mn_{int} + O_{vac}$, the overlap is almost null and then the electrons in the CB can not mediate the

exchange interaction among well separated Mn's. However, these CB delocalized states may contribute to the increased conductivity measured in the samples grown in the Ar atmosphere, although as pointed out previously conductivity must be mostly determined by crystallinity and morphology.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, ferromagnetism is not detected in any of the SnO₂ films, either undoped or 4% Mn doped. The structure of the grown films ranges from amorphous to epitaxial, depending on the growth conditions and substrates and does not modify the magnetic signal which is always paramagnetic. The diffraction and XAS data are consistent with the presence of Mn³⁺ inside the tin oxide lattice for the films grown in Ar/O₂ atmosphere and a combination of Mn²⁺ and Mn³⁺ in those grown in Ar. The presence of secondary phases is discarded but close Mn pairs with antiferromagnetic correlations are most probably the origin of the reduced paramagnetic signal. The samples grown in oxygen free atmosphere (Ar) systematically present lower concentration of magnetic centres which is contrary to a correlation between oxygen vacancies and magnetism. In undoped SnO₂, we attribute the observed paramagnetism to the occurrence of native Sn vacancies. Further, the localized nature of the defect induced magnetic moments levels prevents collective magnetic ordering. Thus, due to the short range of the magnetic interactions, long range order requires a close localization of the magnetic centres in the SnO₂ lattice, which can not be achieved in the dilute regime.

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